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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ
ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

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THE STATE OF OPHTHALMOLOGICAL CARE AND ITS IMPROVEMENT IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETIC RETINOPATHY (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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ANNOTATION

In recent years, a significant increase in the incidence of diabetes mellitus (DM) has been observed in all countries. The World Health Organization (WHO) considers diabetes mellitus as an epidemic of a specific non-communicable disease.

Diabetic retinopathy is a complication of diabetes mellitus that leads to damage to the retinal vessels and the development of microaneurysms, as well as the proliferation of newly formed vessels in the fundus. The problem of early diagnosis and treatment of diabetic retinopathy continues to be one of the urgent problems of modern ophthalmology, this is due to the late appeal of patients with diabetic retinopathy.

Key words: Diabetes mellitus, diabetic retinopathy, fundus.

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OFTALMOLOGIK YORDAM XOLATI VA UNI DIABETIK RETINOPATIYA BILAN KASALLANGAN BEMORLARDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH (ADABIYOT SHARHI)

ANNOTATSIYA

So'nggi yillarda barcha mamlakatlarda qandli diabet bilan kasallanishning sezilarli o'sishi kuzatilmoqda. Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti qandli diabetni o'ziga xos yuqumli bo'lmagan kasallikning epidemiyasi deb hisoblaydi. Diabetik retinopatiya - asoratlari retinal tomirlarning shikastlanishiga va mikroanevrizmalarning rivojlanishiga, shuningdek ko'z tubida yangi hosil bo'lgan tomirlarning ko'payishiga olib keladi. Diabetik retinopatiyani erta tashxislash va davolash muammosi zamonaviy oftalmologiyaning dolzarb muammolaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda, bu diabetik retinopatiya bilan og'rikan bemorlarning kech murojaat qilishi bilan bog'liq.

Kalit so'zlar: qandli diabet, diabetik retinopatiya, ko'z tubi.

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**СОСТОЯНИЕ ОФТАЛЬМОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ И ЕЕ
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ У БОЛЬНЫХ С ДИАБЕТИЧЕСКОЙ РЕТИНОПАТИЕЙ
(ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Аннотация: В последние годы во всех странах наблюдается значительный рост заболеваемости сахарным диабетом (СД). Всемирная организация здравоохранения (ВОЗ) рассматривает сахарный диабет как эпидемию специфического неинфекционного заболевания.

Диабетическая ретинопатия - это осложнение сахарного диабета, которое приводит к поражению сосудов сетчатки и развитию микроаневризм, а также пролиферации новообразованных сосудов на глазном дне. Проблема ранней диагностики и лечения диабетической ретинопатии продолжает оставаться одной из актуальных проблем современной офтальмологии, это обусловлено поздней обращаемостью пациентов с диабетической ретинопатией.

Ключевые слова: Сахарный диабет, диабетическая ретинопатия, глазное дно.

Dolzarbliqi. Qandli diabet jamoat salomatligida eng yirik global muammolaridan biri bo'lib, bir qator epidemiologik tadqiqotlarda qayd etilganidek, jamoat salomatligi va ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishga og'ir global vazifa qo'yadi, garchi ba'zi mamlakatlarda diabetning tarqalishi pasayishni boshlagan bo'lsa-da, so'nggi o'n yilliklarda boshqa rivojlangan va rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda qandli diabetning tarqalishi ko'paymoqda. Xalqaro diabet federatsiyasining (IDF) xisobotiga ko'ra 2017 yilda butun dunyo bo'ylab 451 million kattalar qandli diabet bilan yashayotgan bo'lsa, bugungi kunda agar samarali profilaktika choralari kurilmasa, ularning soni 693 millionga ko'payishi extimoli bor. Bolalar va o'smirlar orasida 1-tur va 2-tur qandli diabetning tarqalishi ham oshdi va 20 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalar va o'smirlarda 1-tur diabet bilan kasallanganlar soni bir milliondan oshadi. [7]

2015 yilda N. Sh. Ibragimova va N.M.Normatovalar tomonidan Jahon qandli diabet jamg'armasining (WDF) "O'zbekistonda qandli diabet bilan og'rikan bemorlarda ko'rlikning oldini olish" loyihasi doirasida Farg'ona, Buxoro viloyatlari va Qoraqalpog'iston Avtonom Respublikasida qandli diabet bilan kasallangan bemorlar o'rtasida DR bo'yicha skrining o'tkazildi. 3 ta hududda 18-67 yoshdagi (kasallik davomiyligi 5-15 yil) 2-tur qandli diabetga chalingan 1587 nafar bemorlar tekshirilgan. Bemorlarda: glikemiya darajasi, HbA1c, xolesterin miqdori aniqlandi, shuningdek oftalmologning tekshiruv quyidagilarni o'z ichiga oladi: ko'rish utkirligini aniqlash, ko'z ichi bosimini o'lchash. Natijalar: 1587 bemorni tekshirish natijalari tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, 2-tur qandli

diabet bilan kasallangan odamlarda DR bilan asoratlanish 56,9% ni tashkil etdi, shundan DR I darajasi - 32,8%, II darajasi - 18,6%, III darajali DR -5,5% va bemorlarning 43 foizida esa DR aniqlanmagan. Birinchi navbatda kasallikning davomiyligi 10-15 yil bo'lgan bemorlarning 52 foizi oftalmolog tomonidan tekshirilgan. Kasallikning davomiyligi 10 yil bo'lgan 2-tur qandli diabet bilan og'rigan bemorlarda DR tarqalishi 45% ni tashkil etgan va kasallik 15 yil va undan ko'p davom etganda bu ko'rsatkich 68% ni tashkil etgan. Uglevod almashinuvi kompensatsiyali bo'lgan odamlar orasida I, II va III darajali DR tarqalishi mos ravishda 11,3%, 3,4% va 2,0% ni tashkil etgan ($p<0,001$). Dekompensatsiyalangan bemorlarning 80% da I, II va III darajali DRning tarqalishi mos ravishda 36,9%, 15,8% va 8,8% ni tashkil etgan. O'zbekistonda 2-tur qandli diabet bilan og'rigan bemorlarda DR chastotasi 56,9% ni tashkil etgan bo'lsa, DR I - 32,8%, DR II - 18,6%, DR III - 5,5%. 2-tur diabet bilan og'rigan bemorlarda DR ning rivojlanishi kasallikning davomiyligiga, uglevod almashinuvining kompensatsiya darajasiga, giperxolesterinemiya va dislipidemiyaga bog'liq. [8].

Bu shuni anglatadiki, bugungi kunda oftalmologiyaning global muammolaridan biri diabetik retinopatiyaning oldini olish va erta aniqlashni takomillashtirishdir. Adabiyotlarda bu muammoga bir qancha yondashuvlar mavjud [1,2].

Turli tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, diabetik retinopatiya (DR) va insult, yurak ishemik kasalligi va surunkali buyrak kasalligi kabi boshqa kasalliklar o'rtasida bog'liqlik mavjud. Buning sababi shundaki, qandli diabet ko'plab organlarning funksiyasiga ta'sir qilishi mumkin bo'lgan tizimli kasallikdir.

DR ning oldini olish va erta aniqlashning asosiy usullaridan biri qandli diabet bilan og'rigan bemorlarni muntazam tekshirish hisoblanadi. Buning uchun turli xil tadqiqot usullaridan foydalanish mumkin, shu jumladan funduskopiya, optik kogerent tomografiya (OCT), retinal angiografiya va boshqalar.

Keyingi yillarda fan-texnika taraqqiyoti DR diagnostikasi va davolashning yangi usullarini yaratishga olib keldi. Misol uchun, ba'zi tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, mashinani o'rganish algoritmlari va sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish DR tashxisining aniqligini oshirishi va kasallikni ertaroq aniqlashga yordam berishi mumkin.

Yondashuvlardan biri skrining usullarini qo'llashdir. Erta skrining qandli diabet bilan og'rigan bemorlarda retinopatiyani jiddiy muammoga aylanishidan oldin aniqlashi mumkin. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, erta skrining qandli diabet bilan kasallangan bemorlarda diabetik retinopatiya bilan asoratlanishni sezilarli darajada kamaytirishi mumkin [3].

Diabetik retinopatiya skriningi butunlay ko'rishni yo'qotmaslik uchun ko'zni o'z vaqtida to'liq oftalmologik tekshirish va davolashni talab qiladigan holatlarni aniqlash uchun zarur. So'nggi bir necha yil ichida yaxshi samarali xarajat nisbati bilan bir nechta xavf omillarini hisobga olgan holda aloxida skrining masofalari(intervallari) taklif qilindi. Biroq, ko'pgina mamlakatlarda umummilliy skrining dasturlari uchun resurslar kam. Bundan tashqari, yangi dalillar shuni ko'rsatadiki, retinal tasvirlar yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari yoki kognitiv buzilish xavfi bo'lgan shaxslarni aniqlashda foydali bo'lishi mumkin, bu kurish xavfini oshiradigan boshqa kasalliklar profilaktikasida diabetik retinopatiya skriningi rolini oshirishi mumkin [10].

Britaniya Diabet Assotsiatsiyasi diabetik retinopatiya uchun har qanday skrining dasturi kamida 80% sezgirlik va 95% o'ziga xoslikka ega bo'lishi kerakligini taklif qildi. Ko'z to'rt pardasi tasvirini tahlil qilishda sezilarli yutuqlarga erishilgan bo'lsa-da, aniqlik jihatidan hamma narsadan ustunroq bo'lgan yaxshiroq algoritmlarni izlab topish urinlidir. Bundan tashqari, tavsiya etiladigan usul minimal darajada salbiy natijalar berishi va oftalmologlarga ko'z tubi tasvirlaridagi shikastlanishlarga e'tibor qaratishga yordam berishi kerak. Olimlar adabiyotlarda DRni oddiy kompyuter skriningida oftalmologga yordam beradigan bir nechta algoritmlar mavjud degan xulosaga kelishdi. Usul tez, tejamkor va aniq bo'lsa, eng yaxshisi hisoblanadi. Bu cheklovlarning barchasi davr talabidir. Tadqiqotchilar uchun eng yaxshi algoritmlarni va samarali o'tkazish qobiliyatini aniqlash juda qiyin. Yosh tadqiqotchilar chuqur o'rganish kabi yangi yo'nalishlarga ega, ammo minimal mashg'ulot vaqtida, aniq shikastlanishlarni o'rganish, eng yaxshi xususiyatlarni izlash va eng yuqori aniqlik ko'rsatkichlariga erishish uchun mustahkam tasniflagichlar mavjud [9].

Shuningdek, zamonaviy tibbiyot muassasasida diabetik retinopatiyaning oldini olish va barvaqt aniqlashni takomillashtirishda diagnostika va davolashning zamonaviy usullaridan foydalanish muhim ahamiyatga ega. [5].

Ushbu usullardan biri optik kogerent tomografiya (OKT) bo'lib, u ko'zning to'r pardasidagi o'zgarishlarni va diabetik retinopatiyaning dastlabki bosqichlarida ularning og'irligini aniqlash imkonini beradi. OKTdan foydalanish tufayli davolanishni samarali nazorat qilish va asoratlar rivojlanishining oldini olish mumkin [6].

Shuningdek shamollashga qarshi va angiogenez ta'sir kuchini susaytiradigan preparatlarini introokulyar in'eksiya qilish, lazer koagulatsiya va vitrektomiya kabi zamonaviy davolash usullaridan foydalanish ham muhimdir. Ulardan foydalanish diabetik retinopatiyaning rivojlanishini samarali ravishda to'xtatishi va bemorlarda ko'rish qobiliyatini saqlab qolishi mumkin.

Ikkinchi yondashuv - davolashning zamonaviy usullaridan foydalanish. Retinopatiyani jarrohlik yo'li bilan davolash, shu jumladan lazer terapiyasi ko'z tubidagi tomir o'zgarishlarining rivojlanishini to'xtatishi mumkin. Bruksning tadqiqoti shuni ko'rsatdiki, lazer terapiyasi past darajali retinopatiyada samarali bo'lishi mumkin [4].

Biroq, diagnostika va davolash usullarini takomillashtirish bilan bir qatorda, qandli diabet bilan og'rigan bemorlar o'rtasida ma'rifiy va profilaktika ishlarini olib borish ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Shifokorlar qandli diabetli bemorlarda ko'z tubi holatini diqqat bilan kuzatib borishlari va muntazam ravishda profilaktik tekshiruvlarni o'tkazishlari kerak. Bemorlar shifokorlarning tavsiyalariga amal qilishlari va qondagi glyukoza miqdorini nazorat qilishlari, shuningdek, uzlarining sog'lig'ini kuzatishlari va ko'rishdagi o'zgarishlarga hushyor bo'lishlari kerak.

Qandli diabet(QD) bilan og'rigan bemorlarning yoshi xavf omili sifatida qaralishi mumkin. Ma'lumki, DR bolalikda juda kam uchraydi. Biroq, balog'at yoshining boshlanishi bilan mikrovaskulyar asoratlar, jumladan, diabetik retinopatiyaning tez rivojlanishi kuzatiladi. Buning sababi shundaki, bu davrda kuchli gormonal qayta qurish sodir bo'ladi, bu juda ko'p miqdordagi kontrainsulyar omillar - gipofiz bezining tropik gormonlari, jinsiy steroidlar, o'sish omillari ishlab chiqarish bilan birga keladi. Bu holatda rivojlanayotgan QD dekompensatsiyasi tana vaznining tez ortishi va natijada insulinga bo'lgan ehtiyojning oshishi bilan izohlanishi mumkin. Jinsiy balog'atga etish davri DR ning rivojlanishi nuqtai nazaridan eng xavfli hisoblanadi [5].

Shuni esda tutish kerakki, diabetik retinopatiyani aniqlash va davolashning aniq tizimini tashkil etish ko'rlik xavfini kamaytirishga olib kelishi kerak, bu boshqa narsalar qatorida sezilarli iqtisodiy samarada namoyon bo'ladi. Diabetik retinopatiya bilan og'rigan bitta bemorni davolash (lazer) uchun yillik xarajatlar davlat ijtimoiy xarajatlaridan (pensiyalardan) deyarli 12 baravar kam ekanligini aytish kifoya.

Shunday qilib, retinopatiyani lazer usullari bilan davolashning arzon tizimini tashkil etish davlat tomonidan to'lanadigan nogironlik nafaqalarini to'lash uchun moddiy xarajatlarni, shuningdek, ishtirok eta olmaslik sababli bevosita yo'qotishlarni hisobga olgan holda iqtisodiy jihatdan foydali bo'ladi. diabetik retinopatiya tufayli ko'rish qobiliyati past va ko'r bo'lgan mehnatga layoqatli yoshdagi ko'p sonli odamlarni ishlab chiqarishda. Albatta, moddiy jihatdan inson azobidan ma'naviy yo'qotishlarni hisobga olish mumkin emas [1].

Ammo shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, qandli diabetning asoratlarining oldini olish uchun turli xil potentsial to'siqlar mavjud. Shunday qilib, JSST ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, diabetik retinopatiya tufayli ko'rlikning yuqori samarali oldini olish uchun asosiy to'siqlar quyidagilardir:

- diabetik bemorlarda diabetik retinopatiya va uning oqibatlari haqida ma'lumot yo'qligi;
- birlamchi tibbiy yordam shifokorlari orasida ko'rish uchun xavfli diabetik retinopatiyaning namoyon bo'lishi haqida tushunchaning yo'qligi, chunki u ko'pincha asemptomatikdir;
- lazer koagulyatsiyasi yordamida davolash samaradorligi to'g'risida tushuncha yo'qligi ;
- birlamchi tibbiy yordam shifokorlarida zarur oftalmoskopik malakalarning yo'qligi;
- diabetik retinopatiyani davolash uchun lazer qurilmalarining etishmasligi;
- diabetik retinopatiyani davolashga ixtisoslashgan tajribali oftalmologlarning etishmasligi.

Xulosa. Shunday qilib, adabiyotlarni tahlil qilish diabetik retinopatiyani erta tashxislash va to'g'ri muvozanatli davolashni tashkil etishni takomillashtirish masalalari bugungi kunda oftalmologiyaning dolzarb muammolaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda.

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